

OA eBooks Data Trust Business Model Development (UPDATED)

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1 Executive summary

In preparation for the next stage of the Open Access eBooks Data Trust, Murphy Mitchell Consultants were engaged to help develop a business model to support the Trust. Based on our collective expertise in scholarly communications — especially around open research, research infrastructures, data, and scholarly publishing — and on semi-structured interviews with representatives from key stakeholder groups, as well as input and feedback from the project team, we have proposed a business model that we believe best meets the needs of the community and the Trust itself. Key findings and recommendations include:

- The Open Access eBooks Data Trust is of interest to publishers, academic institutions/libraries, platforms/aggregators, and funders, and our proposed community-driven business model reflects this
- There are clear and attractive value propositions for the Trust which resonate with these potential customer groups
- We propose a hybrid revenue model that combines membership dues with fees for services targeted at individual customer types
- Based on our projections through 2026, we estimate average annual revenues of around \$550k and average annual costs of around \$392k. By 2026, we predict an operating surplus of approximately \$130k, which will subsequently rise, year on year
- The Trust is therefore predicted to be sustainable, but will require around \$1M of funding to cover short-term development and outreach costs
- Our recommendations are priced for maximum accessibility, penetration, and inclusion
- To ensure the Trust's success, it will be essential to continue to develop and work with communities of practice within and across key stakeholder groups
- The business model should be continually modified over time and as more information becomes available
- The third year of the service (currently 2024) is critical - it should be apparent by then whether the Data Trust is viewed as viable by its markets

The deliverables consist of this final report (updated from the draft presented in 2020) together with a modifiable, multi-year financial plan and a Business Model Canvas (BMC).

The report is designed to work as:

- (1) a handbook for understanding and operating the BMC and spreadsheet
- (2) background, insight, and guidance for the Project Team based on the research, interviews, and industry knowledge contributed by the authors.

2 Background

The Open Access eBook Data Trust is a collaborative project and partnership between the University of North Texas, Curtin University, Educopia, and BISG. Its goal is to create a Data

Trust to improve the measurement and analysis of open access (OA) book usage. In 2018 and 2019, the team received funding from the Sloan Foundation to identify challenges in understanding the usage of OA ebooks and recommend strategies to tackle those challenges. The resulting white paper¹ recommended the creation and development of a shared, trusted framework for coordinating usage data, with the creation of a data trust to oversee that framework.

The Open Access eBooks Data Trust will be a community-owned not-for-profit initiative that provides usage data in a secure, useful, and fair way to all of its members. A guiding principle of the initiative is ethical data sharing and usage. There is a focus on responsible use of ebook metrics, and preservation of the diversity of OA book publishers including library publishers, small presses, publishers in emerging markets, and those in less well-funded disciplines.

The Project Team engaged Murphy Mitchell Consulting (the 'consultants') to develop a business model that will sustain the maintenance and growth of the Data Trust.

A business model provides a framework for the sustainable operation of a business, product, or initiative. Our goal in this project was to identify the various components of the model including the intended customers, value propositions, activities, and resources required to deliver that value. We then compared revenue sources with costs and estimated the likely surplus or deficit. While a business model is not an in-depth operational guide, to running a given business, it provides sufficient structure to be able to establish whether the business is likely to be financially feasible, and to identify price points and market penetration targets.

The final model is intended to be flexible enough to be used for business and financial simulations. For example, if we want to know what the effect would be of raising or lowering the cost of a particular product, the model will show us how that affects the surplus or deficit.

¹ **Understanding OA Ebook Usage: Toward a Common Framework.** Watkinson, Charles; Hawkins, Kevin; Montgomery, Lucy; O'Leary, Brian; Neylon, Cameron; Skinner, Katherine (2018), <http://hdl.handle.net/2027.42/143840>

3 Method

Following an initial discovery phase based on project and meeting records, we conducted discussions with key project members to identify organizational needs and priorities. Once we had a baseline understanding of the Data Trust’s goals, we reached out to industry experts to discuss business models and costs, and then to potential users of the Trust about value propositions and services.

Based on findings from those discussions and our independent research, we developed four user personae for potential customers, and a series of value propositions linked to revenue streams. These were then measured against the costs of key activities and required resources. Finally, those findings were carried through to a five-year financial plan.

Following review by the Project Team, we were asked to revise the report as follows:

1. Break out the content within the current business model canvas (BMC) into two additional variations:
 - a. A BMC solely for a potential multi-stakeholder OA eBook usage data exchange network that provides a common utility service of normalizing cross-platform book usage data to return clean data as an API and offer API-based derivative, aggregate data outputs.
 - b. A BMC solely for an OA eBook Usage data analytics reporting service, that leverages the data coming out of the above data exchange network to provide visualizations, dashboards and reporting services for customer segments with recognized, unmet analytics needs.
2. To help map these project outputs to the project’s supply chain report and data governance mechanisms, we ask that across the report and BMCs, you shift the framing of customers and partners as follows:
 - a. Change “partners” to “data providers”, noting exceptions for key partners who will not be providing data
 - b. Change “customers” to “data users” (for the exchange) or “end users” (for the analytics service), noting exceptions for any customers who are not expected to use data outputs
3. Across all three BMC scenarios (data-exchange, analytics-service, both combined), we ask for additional clarity around the value propositions for the data providers, to help us consider financial incentives for participation, such as revenue sharing or data use discounting models.
4. Across all materials, clarify that the term “book hosting platforms” references both aggregators and e-book hosting platforms
5. Finally, we request your analysis as to whether the data trust exchange function could provide analytics services (combined model) while retaining the trust and neutrality it would need to entice engagement from the data providers it is dependent on.

This version of the report contains our updates based on the revisions requested and additional information provided by the Project Team.

4 Discussions with project members and aligned infrastructure providers

4.1 Project members

As described above, our first task was to establish a more detailed understanding of the Data Trust project team's progress to date, their underlying ethos, challenges, and hopes for the project. Among other insights, we learned how much thought had gone into the prospective Communities of Practice (CoPs²) already established by the Project Team. Based on user-centered design and thinking, the CoPs both support the wider project³ and help develop an understanding of the range of self-identifying communities that would be served by this community-driven initiative. The Trust needs to have strong, clear community governance, as well as mechanisms for seeking and responding to feedback from its stakeholders.

From the technical/leadership team at Curtin University we learned how much work and investment had been contributed to the Data Trust project even before the start of the Mellon grant. We learned about the technological challenges already faced, as well as the anticipated scale of work required for launch and then for operating the Trust. The team has already encountered - or anticipates being challenged by - poor quality (meta)data feeds, scarce resources among small OA publishers, and a lack of common standards. They are aware of previous projects that have tried to serve this space and highlighted some possible partners and data providers to investigate. We discussed scaling issues, the potential size of the Data Trust workforce, the core market, and potential products.

4.2 Infrastructure providers

With the infrastructure provider discussions, we concentrated on supply side (cost) factors, as well as issues around revenue raising (e.g. membership vs services, vs grants, etc), pricing for a global and varied market, and how to balance long-term sustainability plans with intermittent requirements to update technology and services. We learned how important it will be to have some standard definitions of key terms such as 'download' and 'attention' and be clear about what identifiers are going to be used. The importance and value of the improved 'persistability' that this service will provide needs to be conveyed to its potential users.

As it was particularly useful, on the next page, we include a figure and explanation of how one provider envisions and manages their cost liabilities.

² The six CoPs are: (1) Publishing/platforms/services; (2) Library publishers; (3) University publishers; (4) Commercial publishers; (5) Societies and associations; (6) Scholars/authors

³ https://educopia.org/data_trust/

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Starting from the bottom of Figure 1, Resource Costs (*RC*) represent infrastructure, licensing, etc. Usually these are stable and cannot be controlled. Above *RC*, the first green line is labeled *cost* and reflects the total cost of providing the service. The space between the *RC* line and *cost* line are controllable costs, which are generally dominated by the people employed to do the work. The *price* line is simply the amount that is charged to customers. It needs to be far enough above the *cost* line to create a buffer but, critically, cannot exceed the willingness to pay (*WTP*) line, which is at the top of the column. For not-for-profit organizations, the price point needs to be as close as can reasonably be maintained to maximize the value created for customers and avoid accruing large surpluses.

Figure 1: The willingness to pay column illustrates how cost of delivery, price, and willingness to pay impact value provided.

5 Semi-structured interviews with stakeholders

We conducted the semi-structured interviews with Advisory Board members and Technical Advisors during June and July 2020. Two consultants were present for each interview. As well as taking notes, the sessions were recorded for additional clarity (Appendix A provides a basic outline of the semi-structured interview path).

The interviewees came from a variety of organizational backgrounds, including large and small publishers, book hosting platforms (including aggregators), emerging markets, and university libraries.

Overall, there was a high level of support for the Data Trust concept and project. This was due partly to the long-term involvement and engagement of the interviewees themselves, but also due to their respect for the project team members and organizations involved.

This was balanced by a keen understanding of the challenges the project faces. Specific issues raised included concerns about how to balance privacy, anonymization, and data protection against openness and data sharing. For many, especially smaller organizations, there are concerns about availability of development resources.

The subject of which organizations the Data Trust should partner with and seek data from was a major focus. Beyond sector-specific data providers like OAPEN, Project Muse, JSTOR, etc, many publishers expressed interest in the large information technology companies — Amazon, Apple, and Google. While these organizations would make invaluable data providers, there is also recognition that they have very little incentive to participate, as the Trust has no relevance to their business models.

Having articulated some potential risks, the interviewees also provided a number of reasons why organizations might want to get involved. These ranged from seeking to increase technical and market understanding, through to raising reputational profile, or increasing the value proposition of proprietary services. There could be opportunities for a research program⁴, perhaps co-designed between researchers and Data Trust members. Some interviewees were hopeful that the Data Trust would provide commercial opportunities, while others viewed it as a chance to show thought leadership. As one university librarian commented:

“We want to be good members of the community. We want to research and learn and share and adapt.”

As another participant put it:

“The current [OA book publishing] landscape is a mess - with little time or attention being paid to metadata, standards, or understanding of the open access ebooks ecosystem beyond individual organizations.... there is a clear need for a neutral body to address this.”

This brings us to the question of, and need for, a particular kind of consensus-building leadership in this space. The Data Trust provides an opportunity to put the OA eBooks ecosystem into a global/international perspective, where there is currently very little community

⁴ Potentially the information science/librarianship domain could use the Trust’s facilities to investigate questions co-designed with input from interested members. Topics could include long term acquisition trends.

leadership, and best practices and community standards are still at a nascent stage. To quote one interviewee:

“There’s a strong interest in figuring out how to work with OA materials in the standardized ways that they work with paywalled content. There’s a level of complexity in trying to account for things. Books, in particular, are in a nascent period with OA that gives an opportunity to standardize reporting on usage of OA materials. We missed the boat on this with OA journals.”

Several interviewees raised questions about how to balance sustainability with supporting the widest possible participation in the Trust. There was recognition that both the financial and technical barriers need to be as low as possible and, at the same time, that the Data Trust represents a unique opportunity to decrease the capacity gap between global north and south. Taking this wider perspective, several interviewees advised on how the project team might focus their efforts going forward. One pointed out that it is important to be able to articulate the Data Trust’s value chain:

“Who is investing (stakeholders), what are they investing (e.g. funding, time, data), and what represents a return on investment to them specifically?”

There was also a sense that the project team needs to take stock, and adjust its approach over time. For example, it was recognized that, in the first instance, the number of core market segments and distinct value propositions that the Trust aims to serve must be kept as low as possible. Indeed, the cost of supporting multiple API versions and interfaces was cited as a critical risk to sustainability. However, over the longer term, future iterations of the business model could investigate ways of differentiating more finely between the Trust’s customers by examining payment models based on different characteristics, such as per-title versus publisher FTE count versus geographical location.

6 User personae

We synthesized the information and insights from the interviews, together with desk research, our own industry experiences, and internal discussions, to develop four user personae - Publisher, Institution Research Manager, Librarian, and Funder (see Appendix B).

User personae are fictional characters developed to express a particular user type's requirements, preferences, and expectations. They help clarify how different users will respond to and engage with digital tools and interfaces (such as websites or apps) that are being designed and built.

If it is pertinent to the product/service in question, user personae can include demographic details (age, gender, income range, etc.). But the most important elements are a short description of the user type's main requirements and any additional information that is relevant to the particular project. The development of personae acts as a compass for navigating the many decisions that are made during any digital design and build. User personae act as the starting point for all functional and creative decisions, ensuring that the end result is fit for purpose. One additional advantage of creating user personae is that it helps diverse internal stakeholders to come together and understand what the product can and should deliver, and — importantly — what it cannot and will not deliver. By creating user personae that are focused on user requirements and business benefits, stakeholders can see exactly why and how decisions are being taken.

In this instance, the user personae helped to clarify material versus perceptual differences between the different customers. For instance, there is a general pain point of “not enough data” for any of the organizations to be able to make meaningful decisions within their own sphere of activities. Through developing the personae, it became clear that the Data Trust provides the opportunity to plug this gap for the various users, by enabling:

- **Publishers** to refine their marketing strategies (and spend), reduce the time and administrative burden trying to pull disparate datasets together for analysis, and compare their effectiveness (reach, impact, strategic decisions) with a general industry benchmark
- **Librarians** to have an evidence base for proving the impact and value of their institution's research outputs, improving the discoverability of high value resources, pulling OA ebooks into the canon, providing data to enable queries on the value of BPCs, and highlighting which publications or platforms to prioritize
- **Institutional Research Managers** to understand and better support OA ebooks activities within their institution, thus leveling the playing field between scientists and those working in humanities and social sciences, increasing the incentives for all scholars to provide better information about what they are publishing, and so better populate the scholarly record of the institution
- **Funders** to develop and implement open access policies for their funded outputs, receive better information about compliance and return on investment (via usage and reach information), and benchmark their own performance against the industry overall

We have included the complete user persona stories in Appendix B:

- To illustrate our method, and explain how we developed the overall value propositions and business model proposal for the Data Trust

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- To enable the Project Team to test, refine, and, if appropriate, separate out further personae through subsequent work with the CoPs and other project stakeholders
- As a starting point for the Project Team (and eventual Data Trust staff) when developing outreach and communication materials, working with potential customers, and seeking additional funding

7 Business Model Canvas

We used the Business Model Canvas (BMC, see Figure 2) developed by [Alexander Osterwalder](#),⁵ a strategy and innovation tool used by teams to visualize, challenge, and invent business models in a lean, agile, and visually digestible manner. It requires the team to define and articulate what the service is, what problems it addresses, who will value it, and how they will pay. The Canvas also covers how the value will be delivered by defining key activities, required resources, necessary partners, and the primary costs associated with all of those.

Figure 2: Template for a Business Model Canvas

In order for the Project Team to extract maximum utility from the deliverables, we are providing some information on how to use the BMC.

The right side of the BMC focuses on the customer (external) while the left side of the canvas focuses on the business (internal). External and internal factors intersect in the value proposition, which is the exchange of value between the business (running the Data Trust) and its customers/clients.

⁵ See <https://www.strategyzer.com/canvas> and the book Business Model Generation <http://www.businessmodelgeneration.com>

7.1 The value proposition

The value proposition is the fundamental concept of the exchange of value between your business and your customer/clients. Generally, value is exchanged with a customer for money when a problem is solved or a pain is relieved for them by your business.

7.2 Customer segmentation⁶

With the exception of true mass-market products and services like telecoms and food items, customer segments must be identified. In many cases, there will be more than one type of customer, and these should all be listed in the Canvas.

Customers are divided into groups that are similar in specific ways, such as job role, organization type, country, etc. A guiding principle here is that customers should only be segmented out if the business will interact with them in definable and different ways. For example, male and female librarians would not be a meaningful segmentation here, as gender has no bearing on their professional needs or pain points with respect to OA e-books.

7.3 Customer relationships

These are defined as 'how a business interacts with its customers,' whether this is in person, online, via video calls, and so on.

7.4 Channels

Channels are the avenues through which the customer comes into contact with your business and becomes part of the sales cycle. They are generally covered under the marketing plan for the business. Examples include: presentations and networking at conferences, social media, SEO, existing platforms, and targeted blogs.

7.5 Key activities

These are the actions that your business undertakes to achieve the value proposition for its customers. Examples include: technical development, community outreach, and standards creation.

7.6 Key resources

These are the practical resources needed to deliver the key activities (actions) of the business and include offices, computers, hosting, and staff.

⁶ Note that 'Customer' is a standard term in the Business Model Canvas. In our analysis, especially in chapter 11, we break this group down further into 'data users' and 'end users' to add clarity to their place in the mixed and separated business models.

7.7 Key partners⁷

Very few business models require an organization to perform every function in a value supply chain. For example, academic libraries partner with library service providers to provide indexing, discovery, and collection management software. Key Partners are other external companies/suppliers/parties needed to achieve the key activities and deliver value to customers. A subset of key partners for the Data Trust will be 'data providers'.

7.8 Cost structures

Business cost structure is the monetary cost of operating as a business. This includes the cost of key resources, legal and insurance fees, any licences, and additional time not included in the staff calculations.

7.9 Revenue streams

Revenue streams are the way by which the business converts its value proposition or solution to a customer's problem into financial gain. Revenue models include pay per view, fee for service, subscription, dividends, referral fees, and memberships.

Once an organization is able to understand both its cost structure and revenue stream, it is possible to compare the two and identify whether the business model is sustainable or needs to be modified.

⁷ Note that 'partner' is a standard term in the Business Model Canvas. In our analysis we break down partners by type, with 'data providers' a notable category which is treated separately.

8 The Data Trust BMC

See Figure 3 below - a higher resolution version is also submitted with this report, and an Excel spreadsheet version is included in the financial projection file. Where relevant, the sticky notes are color-coded - so, for example, publisher-related information is blue. All cross-cutting entries are coloured yellow.

Figure 3: Data Trust Business Model Canvas

8.1 Customer segments

The customer segments — which evolved from the interviews and then the persona development exercises — are not shown in any particular order.

The Communities of Practice (CoPs) already established by the Project Team, see Section 4.1 above, both support the wider project⁸ and also help develop an understanding of the range of communities that would be served by the initiative. Although they do not correlate directly with the business model’s high-level customer segments (for example, we group several CoPs together under the functional heading ‘publishers’ as, for the purposes of the canvas, they are united by a common value proposition), they will be essential for ongoing community development, including outreach and marketing. They will also be helpful in assessing demand for the Trust’s services among specific professional groups; understanding community specific concerns around governance or participation; identifying emerging trends or pressures on

⁸ https://educopia.org/data_trust/

specific customer segments; and evolving actual conversations with potential customers, pilot partners - including data providers and Mellon.

8.1.1 Definitions⁹

Publishers: The customer segment ‘publishers’ relates to any book publishing organization - whether non-profit, commercial, hybrid, wholly or partly open access, library, or university-owned. We recognize that this encompasses many regional, functional, political, and business model variations. However, regardless of their business model or missions, all publishers need to promote their books, reach researchers (both as authors and readers), and understand their market. So, ultimately, the Data Trust provides the same value proposition to all publishers; the differentials lie in their ability to pay, how they would provide data to the trust, and which product they may wish to purchase (e.g. dashboard or API). The CoPs will enable the Project Team to refine its messaging and build channels to market when the Trust launches.

Libraries: The BMC refers to ‘libraries’ throughout as a proxy for ‘institutions,’ because they tend to have both the greatest interest and the potential capacity to pay for services such as those offered by the Data Trust. While institutional research managers will also have an interest in the reach and impact of OA e-books, and in managing BPCs paid from grants etc., librarians will generally be best placed to interpret the data. As such, as well as the library itself, this category also includes a range of functions and priorities within the institution, including research funding, evaluation, and management.

Platforms: This category refers to both ebook aggregators and ebook hosting platforms. Due to their size and global reach, interest from and adoption by platforms is critical. Without timely buy-in by this segment, the Data Trust will not be viable in the longer term. Throughout the interviews this emerged as a consistent theme. As seen from the financial projection spreadsheet, we have assumed that this will take some time to achieve, but we strongly recommend that the Trust launches with at least one significant platform on board as a clear signal to the others.

Funders: As with the other customer segments, funders differ greatly in their size, interests, policies, and other characteristics. They may be publicly funded, philanthropic foundations, scholarly associations, or academic institutions themselves. However, there is a subset, consisting of the Open Research Funders Group, plus those that have signed up to cOAlition S, that have demonstrated clear commitment to open research and evaluation. In many cases, we know that they have also expressed an explicit interest in OA monographs. These groups share a policy goal of moving scholarly communications to open, so they have a clear interest in tracking the evolution of the market in OA e-books as both a metric of progress and of policy compliance. We therefore see a market among these funders, in particular, for the Data Trust, in order for them to better track impact, evaluate research programs, and assess their return on investment.

Authors: Direct monetization of authors has been historically unsuccessful, so we have labeled them as ‘indirect’ customers, since they will not be making buying decisions or contributing any revenue, but may have access to the Data Trust via their relationships with the other channels.

⁹ Note that some of these organizations work in multiple capacities (e.g. a university may be a publisher, library, funder)

8.2 The value proposition

The Data Trust's value propositions map onto its customer segments as shown in Figure 3 and according to the color coding. Our research indicates that, overall, the Trust should provide stakeholders in the scholarly communications ecosystem with additional business and market intelligence (publishers, libraries); evidence of the value and impact of their work (authors, libraries); an improved service offering for their own customers (platforms); and opportunities to benchmark institutional and individual performances over time (funders).

8.2.1 Publishers

The value propositions of the Trust for publishers include business intelligence (from increased understanding of the OA eBooks landscape and the relative performance of their own work to those of the industry at large, in particular regions and/or in specific disciplines) and market intelligence (bringing the capacity to assess the impact and effectiveness of promotions etc.). Each of these brings strategic and financial benefits for publishers, enabling them to manage their portfolio and to direct investments most effectively.

By providing richer analytics, enhanced evidence of impact, and an overview of their books' performance in the wider OA eBooks market, the Trust will enable publishers to offer an improved experience to authors and gives the potential to develop innovative value-add services which could support author recruitment.

8.2.2 Libraries

For libraries, the value propositions of the Trust lie in improved faculty and institutional support, as evidence of reach and impact will support institutional benchmarking and portfolio management, tenure applications etc.

The intelligence that the Trust will provide will also enable better informed strategic collection management and could be used to improve discovery tools by, for example, top-performing eBooks related to search terms adding currency and context to results.

8.2.3 Platforms

eBook platforms (including those for publishing, aggregation, and discovery) will be able to add value for their clients by showing how platform services and features enhance usage. Evaluating their relative performance and usage share will enable platforms to derive potential competitive advantages with evidence-based feature adjustments or marketing strategies. Understanding trends and shifts in the OA eBook landscape will also help established players to maintain their market position by anticipating trends and consolidating strengths.

8.2.4 Funders

Funders aggregate vast troves of information as part of both grant applications and reporting/evaluations. Being able to benchmark institutional and individual author impacts will enrich the data they use for their evaluation and review processes.

For those funders with open access policies, the ability to discover and track eBooks resulting from work they have funded, and the ability to assess Book Processing Charges (BPCs) and related investments, will provide crucial data to inform and direct ongoing open access

programmes and priorities, not least in the ability to gauge the impacts of their policies on the wider book publishing landscape.

8.2.5 Authors

While authors will not have a direct relationship with the Trust, the integration of Trust data and dashboards in their publisher, library and other services will provide them with detailed, rigorous evidence of the reach and impact of their work. This will support career development, research communication, and, potentially, new channels for outreach and collaboration.

8.3 Customer relationships

The Data Trust's community-led ethos is key to informing its customer relationships. Touchpoints will include the co-creation of standards and the development of community governance.

8.4 Channels

These include consortia, inbound marketing, discovery and aggregation platforms, and API/GUI customers, as well as standard outreach and sales activities, customer support functions, self-service portals, documentation, search engine optimization (SEO), and website discovery.

8.5 Key activities

Key activities include standards development, data security and privacy, stakeholder management, data management/science, community governance, technical development, IT operations, customer support, and documentation.

The need for the operational components of these activities is self-evident, as it would be impossible to provide value without the technology in place. We believe that the community-building and governance aspects of the Data Trust are of equal importance. Many cross-stakeholder initiatives in scholarly infrastructure have failed to scale due to a lack of community uptake. Based on our combined experience, we know that the scholarly communications community attaches particular significance to participation in decision-making and design processes.

8.6 Key partners

During the course of our interviews, we asked interviewees which platforms and publishers the Data Trust should engage with, from early on, to be successful. The scholarly supply chain is complex, with numerous organizations playing one or more roles including publisher, book hosting platform (including aggregator or "secondary publisher"), or discovery layer. In many cases, a single piece of content can appear in multiple places and often in various versions.

A content acquisition strategy is beyond the scope of our work on this project, however, the following organizations were mentioned during our interviews as likely key partners.

8.6.1 Platforms and publishers (data providers)

Initial discussions within the Data Trust have focused on OAPEN as a potential major source of open access book metadata, since they have 5,000 OA ebooks.

A number of other platforms and publishers were also identified as potential sources of data (OA ebook numbers are shown where available).

	# OA ebooks (if known)	Notes
Hosting and discovery platforms		
OAPEN	5,000	
NCBI bookshelf	4,767	OA access subset metadata is available through ftp site
Jstor	3,000	
MUSE	2,000	
ProQuest	-	A mixed commercial platform of licenced content including OA
EBSCO books	-	EBSCO may or may not host OA ebooks, but does index them
Hathi Trust	-	Almost 3M full view books (some are OA, many are public domain)
Apple books	-	Some publishers use Apple books to sell copies of OA ebooks A number of publishers cited this as required
Publishers with their own platform / significant control		
Elsevier Science Direct	47,000	Number of 'Non-subscribed' books in Science Direct KBART records
Wiley Online Library	-	
De Gruyter OA ebook library	>2,000	
Taylor and Francis ebooks	>450	
Sage	-	
OUP Scholarship online	80	
Cambridge Core	81	

Table 1: OA ebooks platforms and publishers

8.6.2 Discovery and library services platforms (channels)

A number of interviewees raised the possibility of using discovery and library services companies as potential channels to deliver analytics to libraries, as well as to enhance user experience or discovery.

OAPEN directly expressed interest in acting as a channel, as they see delivery of analytics to libraries as one of their core business functions. EBSCO, Proquest, and OCLC are also potential channels.

8.6.3 Consortia

Many libraries use consortia as a way to streamline purchasing and combine market power. In addition, some consortia have expanded their role in recent years to include policy work and coordination of technical projects. The value of consortia is therefore two-fold. They provide an important sales channel, particularly for small- to medium-size libraries, as well as being key opinion leaders in the scholarly infrastructure and library communities. Forming close ties with organizations like Big Ten, CAPES, HEAL-Link, Jisc, KESLI, OhioLINK, and SCELIC, as well as ICOLC, would, therefore, have multiple benefits.

Major library systems like California Digital Library and London Public Library in Canada have similar levels of influence and are also potentially valuable data providers.

8.6.4 Related initiatives

There are a variety of related initiatives in the scholarly infrastructure space, some of which may be valuable stakeholders, others may be competitors. This report does not contain a full competitor and threat analysis, however, we are aware of a number of initiatives of interest¹⁰.

As mentioned above, OAPEN see their key business as providing open access usage analytics to libraries and would not supply data to a competitor. If the Data Trust wishes to make use of OAPEN data, they cannot launch a product in this market without OAPEN. Other interesting initiatives include:

IRUS-UK - A mechanism for aggregating usage data from repositories

CORE - An Open University-hosted project to create a cross-repository discovery platform

Scalar, Fulcrum, Vega, Editoria, PubPub, Manifold - Open ebook publishing platforms developed mostly by or in association with universities

8.7 Cost structures

Key costs include personnel, infrastructure, community engagement and marketing, overheads, and travel.

8.8 Revenue streams

The proposed revenue streams are memberships (all segments), dashboard subscriptions (libraries, publishers, funders), and API access (libraries, publishers, funders).

¹⁰ The first version of this report included Crossref's Distributed Usage Logging (DUL) service, a usage logging standard originally aimed at subscription journals but with many potential use cases. This has now been de-prioritised by Crossref and so has been removed from the list.

8.9 Key resources

These include Codebase, Communities of Practice, Mellon support (CAPEX/seed), Project team, Hosting (Curtin/COKI), Advisory Board and Technical Advisors, and COKI.

9 Products and services

For this part of the report, please refer to the ‘Business Modeling Sheets’ spreadsheet, ‘Products & Services’ tab.

Based on the value propositions identified in the BMC, we see two main revenue streams:

1. Memberships
2. Access to data via either a dashboard or an API

9.1 Memberships

Funders, platforms, publishers, and libraries are all potential members. Based on our understanding of successful membership models, as well as feedback from interviewees, the concept, privileges, and responsibilities of membership are important factors for all these organization types in engaging with the community (see the CoPs). The bar to entry should be as low as possible in order to attract the widest possible reach in terms of organization type, size, geography, etc. This, in turn, will ensure a truly inclusive governance group.

Inclusion is vital for the Trust’s sustainability. This has previously been demonstrated in workshops and in, for example, the response of the Open Book Publishers group to the proposal for a centralized Trust and standard, and our interview findings reinforced its importance for the Trust. Community ownership, transparency, and accountability will all be essential. An open membership model will help to assure the widest possible cohort of stakeholders that these factors are “baked in”.

As noted above, even a prima facie low price can be a prohibitive barrier to participation in many parts of the world. We therefore recommend that the Trust establishes tiered charges. For revenue modeling purposes, we used a simplified model, based on an average membership fee of US\$200 per year. Specific tiers and pricing should be developed based on the Trust’s final determination of an appropriate set of metrics for tiering.

In developing our initial tiering proposal, we used the Research4Life model as an exemplar.¹¹ This uses a mix of United Nations, World Bank, and World Health Organization metrics to determine a list of countries that get free or reduced cost access to published research content. We downloaded publisher data from the Directory of Open Access Books, and identified the home country of all the publishers on the list. We then mapped these to the Research4Life eligible country list. None of the DOAB publishers appeared on the ‘category A’ list (for free access) and only 10 appeared on the ‘category B’ (for reduced cost access) list. If, for example, both category A and B countries were granted free access to Trust membership and services, the impact on the sustainability of the Trust would be minimal, and it would remove a key barrier for organizations in those countries that wish to participate in the Trust. The Trust could then determine one or more tiers as appropriate using the same metrics, with cut-off points determined by a transparent process.¹²

By charging a fee greater than the US\$200 average to members from countries highest on the Research4Life indices, and including one or more tiers for countries lower in the indices but not

¹¹ <https://www.research4life.org/access/criteria/>

¹² This analysis is included as a tab in the accompanying business modeling spreadsheet.

low enough to qualify for ‘free’ membership, the Trust could actually increase total membership revenue above the levels used in our initial modeling while enhancing its inclusivity.

The Trust may also wish to consider a fixed discount for start-up companies or not-for-profit publishers as another way to maximise inclusion. ORCID operates such a model, where start-ups receive a 75% discount on their annual membership fee and not-for-profits receive a 10% discount.¹³

Whichever model is applied, it is critical that member organizations have a direct stake in the success of the Data Trust, participate in its governance, and are able to vote on key decisions. To maximize membership levels, we recommend that membership is a prerequisite for participating actively in both data ingest and data feeds.

9.2 Data access services

The data product would consist of the organization’s own data being cleaned up and fed back to it, together with some general context. The distinctions between types of publishers are cultural and political but they would use the same API. Some customers, such as funders, may not contribute data directly, but may qualify for certain privileged levels of information based on their investments in open access books.

We suggest distinguishing between access to a fixed dashboard product, which would offer a standardized view of a members’ own data with comparative and contextual data for additional analytics and insights, and an API product, which would offer those members with the development resources and data science ability to integrate Trust data into their own platforms or analytics systems.

Since a platform could integrate the API and in effect ‘re-sell’ the data to their customers, we recommend that the price of API access be set higher than the dashboard option, to minimize the impact of this cannibalization on the sustainability of the Trust. In our initial modeling, we used a fixed factor of six to model the higher price for API access versus dashboards, but the Trust may wish to explore a more responsive variable model for API pricing, once there is greater clarity on the number and scale of likely platform integrations. Making membership mandatory for downstream platform users could also help to minimize this impact.

We also recommend applying a similar free/reduced cost access tiering mechanism for service charges to that used for memberships, both for consistency and to optimize participation at all levels of the Trust’s activities.

There is some evidence that smaller publishers would be more likely to choose the dashboards, while larger ones will use the API - we have factored this into the pricing points in the first instance.

There could also be an opportunity to develop and sell a widget as a low bandwidth, low- cost, lightweight way for publishers to embed Trust data in their sites or services, or potentially as a tool for authors’ own websites, which could be acquired via their institutions. We suggest re-visiting this concept at a later point in the project.

¹³ <https://orcid.org/about/membership>

9.3 Revenue assumptions

We applied a number of assumptions in assessing the market size (see Table 2) and growth trajectories, based on our own extensive industry experience (with ORCID, Crossref, Readcube, and other initiatives), as well as the interviewees' insights, the market penetration curve (see Figure 4), and the projected resources that the Project Team and Data Trust will have access to.

Market sizing assumptions	
Funders	Based on the known subset of funders with strong interest in OA monographs: cOAlition S plus the Open Research Funders Group
Platforms	Based on the list of platforms cited as critical by interview respondents
Publishers	Based on the number of publishers registered in the Directory of Open Access Books
Libraries	Based on the number of academic libraries in North America and Europe
Consortia	Based on 200 members in ICOLC

Table 2: Market sizing assumptions

We chose to make the most conservative assumptions possible in our modeling. This was to maximize our chances of identifying any potential shortfalls in revenue. As such, our market sizing used the lowest numbers we could find evidence for. Note that, for libraries, we used an estimate of the number of academic libraries in North America and Europe as a proxy for the global number of libraries that would be in a budgetary position to pay for Trust membership (recognizing that many smaller libraries in these regions are not in this position, and many larger libraries in other regions are).

Figure 4: Market penetration curve which demonstrates typical phases of product growth and how that relates to the total addressable market size. During the early adopter phase, market growth is approximately exponential (constant percentage per unit time). Once significant market penetration has occurred, market size effects come into play and growth becomes more linear before leveling off as it becomes harder to find new potential customers.

In projecting market penetration over the first five years of the Trust's operation, we also took a pragmatically conservative approach, although there is some nuance in the projections for each group.

Funders: We assumed that the number of funders with stated policies on OA e-books would continue to grow in coming years, as this has been an emerging trend. Our modeling is based on a steady, slow growth of individual funders adopting relevant policies. Funders may join the Trust later than other groups, if they wait until there is a critical mass of relevant data already available. On the other hand, it is possible that one or more existing or new funder groups will decide to join *en masse*. Note that a small number of funders (Wellcome Trust or the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, for example) have thus far been willing to invest in memberships and participation in open initiatives in support of a larger vision. These funders may be candidates for early adoption.

Platforms: These memberships are critical to the success of the Trust as they are vital data sources. We have been cautious in our modeling, basing it on a low uptake in year one with a relatively quick growth to near complete adoption in year five. Given that this is a small group of organizations, we would expect concerted outreach to improve on our forecasts.

Publishers: Our model forecasts low membership in year one, and accelerating growth over the five years. Given suitable relationships with platforms, professional bodies, and others it should be possible to exceed these forecasts, but we note that if the levels of adoption used in the model are not met by year three, it should be seen as a critical risk to the sustainability of the Trust.

Libraries¹⁴: Our forecasts for library participation are based on memberships only. Marketing dashboards etc. directly to libraries may put the Trust in perceived competition with OAPEN, and lead to their withdrawal from the initiative. We chose to build our projections on the assumption that this situation continues as a worst case scenario. The Trust will need to evaluate this situation: there may be a negotiated way around this, or more detailed modeling based on OAPEN's market position may indicate that the loss of OAPEN data and relationship could be offset by the scale of library adoption. More market research is needed to evaluate this risk and determine an appropriate path forward.

Consortia: Library consortia are a valuable channel for reaching large groups of libraries efficiently, but are unlikely to move forward with group memberships until there is a critical mass of members requesting Trust participation. For this reason, our forecasts of membership growth through this segment are very low. Adoption is likely to develop organically from using consortia as an outreach channel, however, so there should be a dual return on investment in engaging with this group: steady background growth of individual library memberships and longer term growth in group memberships.

¹⁴ Note that we have included library publishers in the publisher segment, and libraries-as-access-providers in the library segment as these functional roles align with two distinct value propositions.

10 Financial viability

Our estimated costs are based on a combination of interviews with the Project Team, Crossref, and DataCite, as well as the OA eBooks Data Trust Grant business plan, and our own industry knowledge.

The current round of Mellon funding is set to run through the end of calendar year 2021, so the Data Trust anticipates launching in 2022, with the model running until the end of 2026. If the start date moves, the five-year model can simply be updated to reflect the shift. While the technical development work needed up to the point of launch is considerable, the main costs from launch are expected to be salaries (including technical staff, one of whom is carried over from the current Project Team).

Based on our projections through 2026, we estimate average annual revenues of around \$550k and average annual costs of around \$392k, resulting in a total deficit of around \$1m, which needs to be covered through bridging funding. By 2026, we predict an operating surplus of approximately \$130k, which will subsequently rise, year on year, indicating that the Data Trust is viable.

Our assumptions are as follows:

- There is currently no physical office cost - this would need to be included if a business centre is established (operating as a purely virtual organization can reduce overheads significantly)
- The travel budget is based on the original Mellon costings but, given the current moratorium on travel, this may need to be revisited
- Some potential line items remain open, to be populated by the Project Team as decisions are made about when the Data Trust organization will launch and where it will be located (particularly as some definitions and inclusions will vary based on geographical location). These include facilities and administrative costs, staff benefits/taxes, marketing and communications, and back office services. A number of questions remain from an operational perspective including how accounting and human resource services will be provisioned on an ongoing basis
- In our financial model, we have assumed that spinning out the organization from its institutional sponsors will be a two-step process. That is, we expect some continued involvement particularly from Lucy Montgomery and Cameron Neylon during initial years
- We have included (currently blank) fields for bridge funding from Mellon, to be populated by the Project Team as appropriate

11 Alternative two-part business model

Following the initial business modeling and legal analysis, concerns have been raised about the ability of the OAeBU Data Trust to ensure trust and neutrality across diverse data providers who are themselves competitors. These concerns have led the Project Team to consider dividing the trust into two separate entities:

1. A data exchange network (DEN) to facilitate structures around data governance and community building, while providing aggregation and normalization services for eBook usage data.
2. A data analytics reporting service (DAR), which would provide dashboards and reporting functions that would add a value layer on top of the normalized and aggregated data assembled by the DEN.

To that end, we have created two additional, separate Business Model Canvases that aim to separate the operating concerns, costs, and revenue lines associated with the two different components of the Trust's work. They also draw out the points of necessary interaction between the two entities.

Please note that this reanalysis is limited to the business model only — creation of new financial projections was out of scope. While it is intuitive to assume that the sum of the two entities will be viable, there will likely be an increase in administrative and technical costs associated with running two separate organizations. In addition, while we have described a potential mechanism for revenue sharing between DEN and DAR, this requires further financial modeling to ensure that both entities are independently sustainable.

Dividing the model into two parts creates a separation in business function that will affect the size of both the potential stakeholder community and of the total addressable markets for products and services. Again, this is beyond the current scope and would require further work. In general terms, the DEN would be focused on community consensus and data governance activities, with a much reduced focus on commercial services, while the DAR would focus on creating products and services built on top of the DEN data. This focus would require the DAR to take a more commercially-focused product management approach, including agile product development, rapid market testing, and an active sales pipeline in order to compete effectively with other providers building products based on DEN data.

This division also affects certain customer segments. The DEN and the DAR have different, though complementary, functions, so their potential customers diverge. For the sake of consistency across all of the OA eBook Data Trust materials, we have divided 'customers' into 'data users' and 'end users'. This then necessitates the sub-definition of both publishers and funders. 'All' publishers are potential end users (so would find value in DAR's offering), but only a subset, called 'large' publishers would likely engage with DEN. In this context 'large' is shorthand for publishers with the ability to develop their own digital marketing and business enablement strategy, rather than the size of its publishing program or staff, though the size and ability of publishers to take on this responsibility are likely to be closely correlated. In the DAR (described in section 11.2) we refer to small to medium-sized enterprise (SME) publishers as shorthand for those organizations that would not have the capability to develop their own data infrastructure and strategy. The value proposition for 'large' publishers includes improvements to in-house analysis through the cleaning and standardization of data, for example, better business and marketing insights or author services. Similarly, we have referred to 'Class 1' funders on the DEN canvas. These potentially have both the interest and the capacity to ingest

data ebook usage data through an API and conduct analyses relevant to their interests. This is in contrast with the 'Class 2' term we have used to indicate funders that would prefer a packaged data analytics and visualization solution.

11.1 Data Exchange Network business model

Figure 5: Business Model Canvas for the Data Exchange Network. A scalable PDF is also available

11.1.1 The value proposition

As in the original business model, the value propositions generally map to customer segments (for the DEN, we are using the term 'data users' instead of 'customers', unless we do not expect them to use data outputs). For the DEN specifically, however, we can articulate a clear central value proposition for the exchange — participation in sector-wide data governance and standards, including access to expertise to clean and curate eBook usage data easily in a way that is compliant with those standards. We have explored the various applications of this central idea from the point of view of each segment.

11.1.2 Data user segments

Publishers

The value proposition for 'large' publishers includes improvements to in-house analysis through the cleaning and standardization of data, for example, better business and marketing insights or author services.

Based on market research conducted by Christina Drummond of the Trust project team, and interviews conducted by MoreBrains, making data COUNTER compliant is a strong value proposition for publishers of all sizes, especially university presses, library publishers, and small to medium size independent companies.

In the original, combined financial projections, we assumed that a significant majority of publishers would be interested in a usage data product that would be delivered either through an API or a dashboard. We did not separately analyze the potential market size for curated, pre-analyzed, pre-visualized data delivered via an API. Access to this type of data product, enabling publishers to generate their own business insights and author services enhancements, may represent a viable value proposition, but careful consideration of channels and total addressable market is required before any decisions are made.

Libraries

Based on our domain knowledge of the scholarly communications and academic library sectors, we believe there may be a value proposition for academic libraries as data providers. We expect that some libraries will host ebooks locally for their own collections, either in their role as content providers or as curators of the output of academics at their institution. We recommend further market research to investigate this suggested value proposition (which may depend on a variety of factors including level of internal IT support and whether the institution is teaching- or research-centered) with the caveat that it has not emerged in discussions so far.

Funders

Based on our previous research, we believe that there is a value proposition for funders as consumers of DEN data. A number of funders have expressed interest in supporting the transition to open scholarship, for example, through initiatives like Coalition S. Many, especially those funding work in the humanities and social sciences, have expressed interest in OA monographs. These funders may see value in the opportunity DEN presents for them to engage with the development of standards and definitions, in order to track the evolution of the sector towards openness and better understand the impact of their own activities.

We note that a subset of funders will have the capacity or desire to integrate an API into their systems. We term these 'class 1 funders' for the purposes of this discussion. Further study of this group of funders is needed before the market size can be assessed.

Platforms

Similar to publishers, platforms have a need to add value to end users through better quality, normalized, aggregated, and benchmarked data. Platforms are technically sophisticated, typically preferring to integrate data services into their existing systems. They are strongly motivated to participate in the data and community governance aspect of the DEN, as well as being consumers of the data.

Authors

As in the previous combined business model, authors are indirect data users. The DEN's services would be more abstract than those provided by a combined Data Trust, so it will be important to work closely with data providers that have a good understanding of authors' needs and wants.

11.1.3 Customer relationships and channels

As mentioned in section 11.1, the focus of the DEN would be on community-building and data governance activities. Data ingest will require a direct relationship between the DEN and any data providers. In the BMC, we reference a self-service approach as a means to minimize the overhead cost of managing those relationships. The most significant impact of this change in focus in terms of data user relationships and channels would be the loss of the data analysis and visualization platform as a channel to reach data users. Rather, there would be a shift to the unified API as the sole mechanism for delivering data exchange services.

The primary mechanisms for managing relationships in this new scenario would be via standards and other forms of community engagement, supported by an informational website and web-based administrative interface. This shift will require a strong focus on outreach activities.

11.1.4 Key activities and resources

This section of the BMC is unchanged from the unified model, however, the nature of some activities will be different. For example, 'data management & science' will no longer include visualization, but will be focused on curation and standards. Support and documentation will have a narrower focus, but extra care will be needed to avoid confusion between DEN and DAR documentation.

Some activities and resources will have a narrower scope. For example, the technical aspects will be refocused on core activities of the DEN, including careful coordination with the DAR in particular.

11.1.5 Key partners

The relationship between the DEN and the DAR will be critical to the success of a two-part model. The two organizations must be fully aligned, working together as well as alongside other dashboard and analytics providers, to ensure that the data governance decisions are compatible with the visualizations and insights required.

Data Providers

Publishers, libraries, and book hosting platforms remain key sources of data for the trust. It will also be necessary to work and coordinate with related initiatives such as those mentioned in section 8.6.4.

11.1.6 Cost structures

The main costs associated with running the DEN fall under the same headings as those required for the combined model. The DEN will require its own organizational structure and, as mentioned above, the nature of many key activities will have to be re-scoped. A careful analysis of costs will, therefore, be required to ensure the DEN's viability.

We have added an item for data contribution discounts, because we believe that incentives will be needed in order for data providers to create high-quality, standards compliant data that minimize the curation and cleaning burden undertaken by the DEN. We recommend developing incentive structures in consultation with key data providers, which should then be included in the cost profile of the model to ensure that the model scales appropriately.

11.1.7 Revenue streams

We indicate that the DAR is a critical revenue source for the DEN. Precise modeling of the revenue share relationship between the two organizations is beyond the scope of this report. We recommend that the relationship between the two organizations is carefully modeled to ensure sustainability for both the DEN and DAR, while also being transparent and fair to other analytics and dashboard providers.

Other sources of revenue include data usage fees, which should be tailored to data user types, including publishers looking to enhance their offerings and other dashboard providers. For clarity, data usage would be achieved via access to the API, rather than by dashboards or similar products. Equitable access to the API is a key component in ensuring that the DEN is not seen as a 'competitor' to key platform partners.

There may also be an opportunity for a data consultancy service to help organizations generate data that can be ingested by the trust. This aspect of the model is needed to both enable and incentivize data providers to improve their data pipelines for ingest into the trust. Such a model could be built around tiered ingest fees. Poorly structured data would incur a fee for cleaning and standardization, with the provider's data being returned to them improved. Additional fees could be charged for any additional contextual data provided. Data providers sharing well structured and standards-compliant data might receive a discount and/or access to additional contextual data as a reward for their improved data quality. This has the dual benefits of covering the ongoing cost of data ingest for the Trust, and incentivizing data providers to adopt standards, which in turn will lower the ingest costs for the Trust.

Finally, memberships should remain an important part of the DEN revenue model.

11.2 Data analytics reporting business model

Figure 6: Business model canvas for the data analytics reporting service. A scalable PDF is supplied alongside this document

11.2.1 The value proposition

The value propositions for the DAR are focused on providing services that enable customers (or more precisely 'end users') to directly meet their users' needs. They are, therefore, more granular and will require specific solution development, including user journeys and UX design.

11.2.2 End user segments

Publishers

The target publisher market for the DAR comprises the long tail of organizations that are unable to develop their own analytics engines and dashboards. As a shorthand, we refer to these publishers as SMEs, although it is possible that some larger publishers may opt for a packaged analysis and visualization solution at least in the short term before implementing an integration for the DEN API. While a specific financial projection has not been carried out for this, the dashboard product in the combined financial projections would be a good starting point for this product.

Libraries

Many institutional libraries are interested in strategic collection management and improving the discoverability of content available to their patrons. There are many uses for appropriately

designed dashboards and analyses of OA ebook usage that, combined with data, will help demonstrate and enhance the reach and impact of an organization's reach and impact.

Careful product management will be required to ensure alignment of product roadmaps with end user needs and what it is technically feasible to deliver, so many of the suggested use cases with the market analysis study conducted internally will need to be validated for feasibility.

Funders

Many funders have a strong interest in open access, and in tracking the impact of their activities, but lack the technical capabilities, vendor relationships to independently conduct these analyses, or may not prioritize such work internally. We refer to these funders as class 2 funders in the BMC. The DAR could work with such organizations to provide analysis, visualization, and benchmarking to improve their internal decision-making but, again, there is a need to fully define their needs so that the market can be sized.

11.2.3 End user relationships and channels

As stated in section 11.2.1, the DAR's focus would be on product management, rather than community consensus or data governance and standards, so the end user relationships and channels will be different from those of the DEN. They will need to more closely resemble a commercial organization, with a focus on traditional digital marketing and sales.

Sales channels should include consortia, but not other dashboard or analytics providers who would be competitors to the DAR.

11.2.4 Key activities and resources

In order to be viable, the DAR will need to create a compelling user experience that can compete effectively with other analytics and visualization providers. Key activities should include focus groups, user journey mapping, solution design, agile product ownership, and usability testing. In addition, the DAR will need a sales and marketing team to raise awareness and convert sales leads into revenue.

'Data from DEN' has been added as a key resource here.

11.2.5 Key partners

The most significant partner - and the data provider - for the DAR will be the DEN — the relationship between the two is critical. DEN's data must be fit for purpose for the services being provided by DAR but, at the same time, DEN's governance must be transparent and avoid any appearance of favoritism.

There may be opportunities to work with other platforms to resell or white-label DAR's dashboards. This possibility will require market analysis and modeling to confirm.

Related initiatives have been removed from the DAR Business Model Canvas, since they would not be core to the model. However, it would make sense for DAR to engage with the community and related initiatives in order to maintain good relationships.

11.2.6 Cost structures

The essential cost structure for the DAR aligns with the unified model, with the exception of the need for revenue-sharing with DEN through their data usage fees product. Please note that the financial projections developed for the unified model may not be valid for DAR. The cost of the data usage fees, in particular, must be modeled very carefully to ensure a balance between the need for both the DAR and DEN to be sustainable, while still ensuring transparency and fairness towards DAR's competitors that would have to pay for the same data.

11.2.7 Revenue streams

Aligned with the value propositions outlined in section 11.2.1-2, the DAR's revenue would come from selling dashboards and data analytics services to publishers, libraries, and funders.

Financial projections for the revised two-part business model are out of scope for this report, but we recommend that careful consideration is given to the viability of the DAR, price tolerance of the end user categories, and the costs associated with acquiring data from the DEN.

11.3 Considerations for a two-part model

11.3.1 The case for separation

The primary motivation for considering a two-part model is to avert governance challenges around the creation of a combined Data Trust that both curates and aggregates data through community consensus and data governance, and also sells analytics and dashboarding services to the community.

The need to maintain trust, transparency, and neutrality is critical to ensuring the community buy-in needed for the success of the Data Trust. Selling data to analytics product and service providers, while simultaneously competing with those same providers, raises a potential conflict of interest. OAPEN, a key potential data provider for the Trust, has already expressed concern about the risk of competition with its own planned data dashboard offerings for libraries.

Splitting the Trust into a community-governed organization to facilitate data exchange (DEN) and a commercially-focused data analytics provider with a suite of products and services (DAR), may mitigate this potential conflict of interest, as the DAR would be just one organization among several that would purchase data from DEN and add an analytics/visualization layer.

11.3.2 Challenges posed by the two-part model

Dividing the trust into two parts creates a number of operational difficulties, most notably the relationship between the DEN and the DAR. To be seen as separate entities, with no conflict of interest, they must operate independently. DAR's role in data and community governance issues must be no different than those of any other service provider providing dashboards or analytics based on DEN data. If the DEN/DAR relationship is seen as too close by competitors and/or the community, the reputational risk for the Trust is arguably greater than it would be for a single, combined entity.

Financial projections for both DEN and DAR were outside of the scope of this report but should be developed in order to balance a number of real concerns with regard to revenue share and cash flow:

1. The pricing offered to DAR by DEN must use the same scale being used for other data users of the same class.
2. The pricing must enable sustainability of both organizations without disadvantaging other users of the DEN data.
3. Market sizes for the respective DEN and DAR customer segments (namely data users and end users) must be reassessed, as our original model is not guaranteed to be valid for the new two-part model.

11.3.3 Recommendations for further work to validate the two-part model

Before committing to splitting the organization into two separate entities, we strongly recommend further investigation, including: qualitative business model validation through further discussions with stakeholders; and quantitative financial modeling and projections to ensure the sustainability of both entities.

Specifically we recommend addressing::

- The markets for all customer segments and value propositions, particularly for:
 - Publishers - now showing as a 'general' category with subsets 'large' that indicates a significant level of technical data independence and SME, which represents publishers that don't fit into this category.
 - The differentiated customers themselves
- Possibility of a value proposition for the DEN in relation to libraries
- Definitions for Class 1 and Class 2 funders based on capability and appetite for API integrations, to enable market sizing for DEN and DAR independently
- A revenue share / data usage fee structure that is fair to both the DAR and to competitors using DEN data
- Value propositions for the DEN for funders. Our original analysis suggests that one exists, but it was not covered in the additional market research conducted by the Project
- Cost structure and revenue projections for both organizations

11.4 Feasibility of data analytics services through the combined model

The motivation for splitting the Data Trust into two organizations is twofold.

1. In a response to "Building a Trusted Framework for Coordinating OA Monograph Usage Data" from OBP, Rupert Gatti *et al* raised governance concerns about the supposed neutrality of a centralized Data Trust, which combines analysis of usage data, storing of data and collection from multiple platforms. Similar concerns have been raised in subsequent stakeholder conversations.
2. There is a concern that providing both data exchange and analysis / dashboard services will place the Data Trust in competition with key data providers that may themselves want to provide dashboarding services. In particular, OAPEN has expressed concern that it would impact the profitability of a library dashboard product that they plan to develop and launch.

While objections on the basis of transparency and governance are understandable and merit serious consideration, they are not insurmountable. We believe it would be possible to mitigate these concerns through appropriate governance structures that create consensus across the community around data standards and best practice. If this aspect of the Data Trust's work was conducted in the open, it would create a highly defensible position. Further, the delegation of standards governance to a suitable community organization would reinforce the assertion that the Trust, and the various interest and working groups that it would sponsor, are behaving in the best interests of the community.

The alternative approach of dividing the Trust does not, in our analysis, solve the underlying conflict of interest problem. In fact, we believe it could exacerbate the risk. The necessarily close relationship between the DEN and the DAR could create the perception that the separation was put in place for appearance's sake and may be seen as disingenuous. We recommend that the objections to centralization of the Data Trust be overcome through strong and transparent community governance rather than by creating a separation between two organizations that might be seen as artificial. The Project Team has already made considerable progress in building communities of practice that are fleshing out understanding of, and ramping up engagement among, a range of stakeholders. This work (in both the communities themselves, and the fact they stand as evidence of the project's commitment to these high standards of integrity) provide a basis for further progress in this area.

The second challenge concerns competition between the Trust and other dashboard providers. In our analysis, the Trust is in a strong position with respect to this risk. As an aggregator, it is able to leverage network effects that incentivize participation. The reciprocal nature of data exchange means that any organization that does not participate will be at a disadvantage compared to other platforms. In addition, the sharing of usage data and provision of services on top of freely available data are in the spirit of open scholarship and are practices embraced by the community. Refusal to participate in the trust would represent a significant reputational risk for any organization and would therefore be an unlikely outcome.

12 Concluding remarks (updated)

Through a series of interviews with team members, stakeholders, and potential customers of the Open Access Data Trust, combined with our own desk research and product management experience, we have gathered a significant evidence base to support strategic decision-making for the project.

Based on that evidence, for the initial phase of this project we conducted a thorough analysis of the market needs, value propositions, potential revenue streams, and associated costs for the OA eBooks Data Trust. Using conservative estimates, we concluded that a unified Data Trust would have a number of monetization options available to it, which should enable it to be viable and sustainable with an additional \$1M of bridging funding.

We highlighted a need for the Trust to work on a more thorough content acquisition strategy, to ensure that the value of the data set gathered is maximized. In addition, we noted that care must be taken to ensure the governance and participation structures are inclusive by design.

Following the initial business modeling and legal analysis, the Project Team conducted further research and established that stakeholders are concerned about the ability of the Data Trust to ensure trust and neutrality across diverse data providers. In addition, concerns about competition with other platforms that might provide analysis services led to a proposal to divide the trust into two parts: a data exchange service and an analytics platform.

This extended report takes the first steps in identifying how this might look in terms of revised value propositions and customer segments. It also highlights some possible implications for this step (including financial and reputational) as well as where additional work should be undertaken to minimize confusion across the model, duplication of effort, and other potential risks.

As indicated in chapter 11, above, we do not believe that the separation of the Trust into two organizations would achieve the desired result. It would add overhead, whilst creating a possible conflict of interest that could be mitigated by openness and neutrality enshrined in a clearly articulated and enforced community governance model. If competition concerns from prospective data providers led them to withdraw from the Trust, the reputational harm to them would outweigh the potential damage to the Trust. As such, we recommend that a single organization, that builds on the successful community that the project has already created, be established as the most appropriate and viable way forward.

NOTE: The appendices are numbered because of google doc limitations. The numbers will be stripped out prior to export and then renumbered using word before final typesetting

Appendix A Discussion outline for OA eBooks Data Trust BM interviews

Housekeeping. Introductions of consultants and interviewee as appropriate. Check it's OK to record - for internal purposes only. We won't be reporting back identifiable responses to the Project Team unless they are comfortable with us doing so.

Background: Everyone is on the Advisory Board - apart from Susan Doerr, who is a Technical Advisor, so they are all at least a bit familiar with the project and have, to some extent, opted in. The whole group that we're speaking to is:

Jon Elwell (EBSCO/GOBI), Jill Emery (Portland State University Library and COUNTER), Eelco Ferwerda (OAPEN, OASPA, and OPERAS), Andrew Joseph (Wits University Press), Jo Lambert (JISC), Ros Pyne (Springer Nature), Susan Doerr (University of Minnesota Press)

We already spoke to DataCite and Crossref about costs. Now we're looking at value propositions, business models and possibly revenue streams/amounts.

The BMC is here:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1AnafJlhCUtitTVSUFXrv0kMT56KZPIH4H0ovSZpxmxM/edit#gid=0>

Outline of proposition: To take in usage data (still awaiting more exact definition) relating to OA books from various platforms, aggregate, and provide a dashboard showing usage. Could include mentions, geographic information, etc. Our thinking is that there's potential value in understanding relative performance of different books. If the data can be fed through in real time then specific marketing activities can be measured. Where are the collaborations/where is the interest? Does this provide value to funders? Authors? Publishers? Others? Is Plan S a factor?

Q - what do they think?

Q - how would their organisation fit in with this value chain?

Q - what is the size of their programme or interest?

We've had some thoughts about how a pricing structure might work - could be tiered membership (FTEs), or based partly or solely on outputs or usage by the member?

Do you see benefits for your organization in being an early adopter?

What would they need to be able to take part (either in a pilot or the real thing) in terms of documentation and/or technical support?

Are there specific data providers (thinking EBSCO for instance) that would be necessary for the service to be worth joining?

MORE+BRAINS

A standard for sharing these data would streamline the process of collecting, sharing, and aggregating them. Would you be more or less comfortable if the trust itself maintained the standard, or if it was passed on to an external standards body or community group?

What's the best charging model - membership as total contribution, purely service charges, or membership plus service charge? Discounts (that aren't too dangerous to long term value proposition and sales)?

Q - who do they think would pay, and how much?

Wrap up

Thank you, stop recording, next steps (feed into the model, may follow up by email, final refinements early 2021) Anything else?

Appendix B User personae

B.1 Publisher

As an acquisitions editor, my job is to acquire the highest quality and most impactful content for publication as part of our books program.

I'm interested in acquiring content that is likely to get read and cited many times. A real success for me is when an author's profile is significantly enhanced by our publishing their book. It might be that it helped them get tenure, they may be invited to speak as a keynote, their book may get included in university reading lists. In rare cases, cross-over success can mean that a book becomes popular outside of academia.

B.1.1 Pains

It's really difficult to get a handle on what sort of books are going to be successful. For print, there's no way to tell how many times a copy gets read, but at least you know how many have been sold. Back when print was king, the calculation was simple. The books that sold the best, were the best and they made more money for both us and the author.

Non-OA ebooks are more complicated than print because they are sold in more ways. The advent of collections of books obfuscates the direct value proposition of the individual title. The quality and coherence of the whole collection becomes more important.

OA ebooks are even harder to evaluate. There are no sales figures, so we're reliant on usage statistics. Since we don't have a monopoly on the channel by which readers access content, it's impossible to count all of the usage. Without those numbers, it's hard to tell authors how successful their work is. We try to use other measures of success like bookmetrics, but the infrastructure around the tracking of things like mentions in curricula and in the media is not as developed as it is for journal articles.

B.1.2 Gains

If I were able to supply my authors with a more accurate accounting of how many times their book has been read, it would make the value that we're providing to them more concrete and tangible. It would give them a reason to publish with us, rather than putting their work in an institutional repository and forgetting about it.

We could also test promotional approaches to see if we can drive usage. Does an online marketing campaign help with usage, for example. What about driving coverage in the media, or inclusion in a MOOC? Does social media outreach using twitter, or instagram work best?

Taking this a step further, it would really help us make better editorial strategy decisions, if we were able to compare usage data with metadata about our books. We could look at which subject areas are doing well. Does the institution they're at make a difference? What about cross-disciplinary topics, or subjects that align to the UN sustainable development goals? Do they get more reads?

B.1.3 Gain creators

Bringing together all the data in one place would help me provide more complete data to authors to show the value that we're providing. That would also be useful as a sales tool that I could show to prospective authors, not only as an example of the kind of data we could provide if they publish with us, but also as aggregated data across our portfolio to show how effective we are as a publishing company.

Looking at data in some kind of visualization at the book level would be useful to compare against social media and other marketing data, to inform marketing and promotional strategy. Aggregating it across metadata like subject headings and being able to compare our books to other publisher's works would help us figure out what to publish more or less of.

B.1.4 Pain relievers

The Data Trust would bring all the usage data from multiple platforms into one place, reducing the amount of work needed to collate it. It would also reduce my anxiety that I'm missing some data. If we could bring in data from other systems like bookmetrix, or other event data, that might help us get a clearer understanding of the total impact of a book.

B.1.5 Products and Services

A dashboard that shows the usage data aggregated across all of our books, with the ability to facet it by author, subject area, geographic region. Comparing data to an aggregated baseline derived from all publisher's data may be of value.

A dashboard, or author services widget that is specific to an author to show how well their work is doing.

For more technically capable publishers, this could be replaced by an API that would enable publishers to import data into their own systems.

B.2 Librarian

As a librarian, my job is to facilitate access to information resources for our library users. I want users to be able to discover and access resources as easily and swiftly as possible. Offering discovery and indexing tools to ensure they can find the right resource at the right time is a critical part of our service offering.

I want our users to recognize and value the contribution the library makes to their learning, teaching, and research activities, to feel that we are providing them with access to a highly relevant pool of resources, and to support them in locating resources that may not form part of our core collection.

B.1.6 Pains

Users really don't realize how much we provide. They find things on Google, and don't know that they can only access that resource because we paid for a subscription. They also don't often realize how much we pay in APCs, BPCs, and read-and-publish deals with publishers to make sure they have seamless access to publishing services as both authors and readers.

Open Access resources don't pass through our usual acquisitions and accessioning workflows, so they often won't show up in our catalogue. Our own OA collection in the repository is incomplete and only tracks downloads from the repository itself. We struggle to track the complete usage picture for that content. If an item is on a reading list, we really can't be sure how (or if) the readers access that book.

We also struggle to prioritize the limited support we have for OA book publishing. Various models are used to pay for OA monographs, and we find it hard to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of each one, and of various publishers, and to give the right guidance and support to our authors. Understanding how books are used across disciplines and regions would be a big help for us in developing an accurate picture of what constitutes high usage or impact in a given area.

B.1.7 Gains

Understanding which books are actually being used, and how, would make our discovery services much more useful. For instance, we could surface 'hot' titles in subject search results.

We'd like to encourage our authors to post more content in our repository and, if doing so enabled them to get a more complete picture of the reach of that book, it would be a more attractive option.

Being able to map trends and big hits (in a meaningful context) would enable us to make more strategic choices about which publications or platforms we prioritize. If we're being asked to invest in a BPC, for instance, it would be great to evaluate the outcome of that, both in terms of absolute numbers of users, and also compared with other books in the field. Knowing what success should look like is vital if we are to recognize it.

B.1.8 Gain creators

A way to track the hosting and discovery mechanisms for OA eBooks would give us a much more complete picture of how content is being used. For instance, we would be able to see what the 'bestsellers' are - high usage either in absolute terms, or in relative terms for the field at a particular moment would be super helpful.

A mechanism that enables us to track books produced by our own authors, wherever they might be hosted, and that could show us how they perform compared with other books, or where they are mentioned or discussed, would help us to help our authors to demonstrate their impact, and to show university management how the research publishing portfolio is performing.

Being able to understand and compare usage of ebooks in different platforms and venues would help us to manage our collection policies and determine which discovery solutions or hosting platforms are proving most popular with our readers.

B.1.9 Pain relievers

Better data about what is published, and where it ends up being both hosted and used, would help us to justify our expenditure on BPCs and support for publishing. It would also help us to evaluate the cost effectiveness of our read and publish and similar deals with larger publishers.

Being able to show not just downloads from our repository, but also downloads and views from other platforms, would help us to showcase the value that OA brings to our collection.

B.1.10 Products and services

Integration with library management systems to power new discovery and promotion tools.

Bringing in complete usage data that can be broken down by groups of books, individual books, authors, etc. to enable multi-faceted reporting and analytics.

Benchmarking and comparison tools with data about trends in publication and usage patterns in different regions and disciplines, to enable evaluation of past performance, and to inform predictions of future priorities.

B.3 Institution

As a senior research support manager at a mid-sized university, my role involves tracking and reporting on our research outputs for various internal and external evaluation exercises, advising on and developing research funding proposals, and maximizing our researchers' compliance with funding mandates and policies. We're increasingly being encouraged to support Open Access publishing, for which there is some funding within the institution.

B.1.11 Pains

I frequently have to nag people to input information and upload files to populate their institutional profiles, which is no fun for anyone. I get complaints about repetitive administrative tasks that disrupt scholarly activities, and information that should be richly informative is often omitted as people simply upload the minimum amount of information they can get away with. This, in turn, affects the accuracy and utility of the reports and evaluations I need to run for senior managers and external stakeholders (e.g. for our periodic national research evaluation process).

I'm aware there are potential data points and connections that we could be monitoring, but aren't, and suspect this is holding us back from improving our research programme. There is a huge amount we simply don't know about our research outputs' existence outside of the institution.

I can see that our scientists, who publish in journals, are far better served with automated information feeds than our social scientists and humanists, who generally publish books and book chapters. For the latter, not only are the information feeds slower, less standardized, and so less meaningful, but metrics such as citations often accrue very slowly, and impact outside of academia (so anything involving media attention or policy) is basically invisible.

While I am aware of the Open Access policies for many of our funded outputs, this is much clearer with journals publishing than books. In particular, while many scientists can directly connect their grants with their published outputs —and so secure or allocate funds to publish OA — the HSS researchers often develop a single book on their own without any direct funding. How do we support Open Access in these instances?

B.1.12 Gains

If there were an automated way of accurately collecting data about the OA books - their usage, mentions in social and other media, etc - that would make a huge difference to various aspects of my role. We would have a much better sense of how, and by whom, the books are being used. We could show the ROI on investing in OA by looking at usage beyond the academy and in Lower and Middle Income Countries. When academics are preparing their cases for promotion and funding, they would be able to include much richer, more storied, information to put their specific contributions to their field into context. We would also be able to better understand emerging fields, connections between disciplines, and how our researchers collaborate with others.

There would be a decrease in the amount of repetitive administrative tasks that irritate everyone so much, and I could envision spending less time working on the various reports I have to prepare for department and institution-level decision-making.

Personally, I like the idea of being able to provide a more discipline-equal service to the HSS researchers, who currently have a relatively impoverished experience in terms of how their reach and impact are understood. This sort of information may help leverage their claims for OA funding for their publications, which in turn would help our stated mission to support Open Scholarship.

B.4 Funder

As programme manager for a national research funder in HSS, my job is to ensure we are developing the right calls for proposals in high-value fields, operating a fair assessment and allocation system, funding the right people to perform research, and fulfilling our wider goals: to provide impact and value for our stakeholders - the academic communities we serve, policy makers, and taxpayers. As part of our remit, we are increasingly encouraging our researchers to publish their findings as Open Access books and chapters. This fulfils our commitment to Open Access and Open Scholarship in the longer term.

B.1.13 Pains

As a funder working in the humanities and social sciences, I'm frustrated by how hard it is to track interest in and the impact of the outputs that we have funded. While my counterparts working in the hard sciences can rely to some extent on the journal article ecosystem (which is imperfect but better funded) to provide evidence, for example, through article citation counts and COUNTER-benchmarked usage statistics, we are reliant on very piecemeal information. Meanwhile, various mandates, such as Plan S, the national research evaluation exercise, and other benchmarks, are becoming increasingly arduous to address and comply with.

B.1.14 Gains

If I had more and better usage data available, it would be a comparatively simple process to start tracking our impact as a funder. It would also help us to gain a sense of impact over time, and to understand how collaborations and international interest are building. How does our funding compare with other funders in our field(s)? Are there gaps in functionality of the system that still need to be plugged in order for us to be able to derive still more benefits in the future? As a national funder, do we have some responsibility for investing in research infrastructure? If so, how can we do that equitably?